

Conductometric and Spectrophotometric Studies on Scandium(III)-, Yttrium(III)- and Lanthanum(III)-3,5-Dinitrobenzoate Complexes

R. M. AWADALLAH and A. A. M. GAD

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Aswan, A. R. Egypt

Manuscript received 9 August 1982, revised 24 December 1983, accepted 9 March 1984

The interactions between scandium, yttrium and lanthanum with 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid (DNBA) have been studied conductometrically and spectrophotometrically. The spectrophotometric studies indicate that the complexes Sc^{3+} -, Y^{3+} - and La^{3+} - 3,5-dinitrobenzoates are formed in buffer solutions of pH 9.1, 6.4 and 8.59, and absorb at 217, 235 and 220 nm for Sc^{3+} -, Y^{3+} - and La^{3+} -DNBA, respectively forming 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 (M. R.). Complexation takes place through covalent bond between the metal ions and the carboxylate group which leads to the formation of salt like complexes. The stability constants (K_f) are evaluated from the results of the spectrophotometric measurements and the free energy ($\Delta^{\circ}G$) values of the complexes. The order of stability constants has been found to be $Sc^{3+} > Y^{3+} > La^{3+}$.

3,5-DINITROBENZOIC acid (DNBA) was used for the preparation of Pb-DNB¹ and for the gravimetric determination of Th(IV)². Sc(III), Y(III) and La(III) were studied spectrophotometrically using dibenzoyl methane³, violuric acid⁴, murexide⁵, mixed violuric-murexide ligands⁶, and pH metrically using ethyleneglycol-bis (β -aminoethyl ether) tetra acetic acid⁷ as a ligand.

Experimental

Standard solutions: Metal ion ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) solutions were made by dissolving the A. R. grade (99.9%) $Sc(NO_3)_3 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Y_2(SO_4)_3$ and $La(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ in double distilled water. Standardisation was done following the gravimetric determination of the elements⁸. Weaker solutions were prepared by diluting appropriate volume of the stock solutions. **Reagent solutions:** $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid was prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of the ligand in absolute ethanol (BDH). **Buffer solutions:** oxalic, boric, succinic acids, sodium sulphate, borax and sodium carbonate buffer solutions of pH 1.5-11 were prepared by mixing the appropriate volume of these solutions⁹ and standardised by a pH meter.

Pye Unicam Model 290 MK2 pH Meter, Pye Unicam SP 8000 Ultraviolet Recording spectrophotometer, and Solu. Bridge REG. US. PAT. OFF, RD, BL5, conductance bridge were used for recording the respective data.

The conductometric titrations were carried out by titrating a certain concentration (V_1) of the metal ions with 0.5 ml increments of the ligand (V_2), then measuring the conductance values after stirring the solution for two minutes by a magnetic stirrer

and correcting the specific conductance due to dilution ($\lambda \times \frac{V_1 + V_2}{V_1}$). Conductometric measurements were carried out using constant concentration of the metal ions and variable concentrations of DNBA keeping the total volume constant, thermostating the solutions at 30° for two hr. The spectrophotometric measurements of the test solutions prepared by mixing the metal ion with the ligand-buffer mixture against reagent blank solutions were made.

Results and Discussion

Electrical conductivity measurements :

The conductance values obtained during the titration of Sc^{3+} -, Y^{3+} - and La^{3+} -DNBA solutions increase gradually with the increase of ligand concentration due to liberation of hydrogen ions, thus increasing the conducting power of the solution and formation of salt like complexes (electrolytes). The conductometric studies indicate that the metals react with the ligand to form mainly three types of complexes, 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3.

Spectrophotometric measurements :

The spectrograms of Sc^{3+} -, Y^{3+} - and La^{3+} -, 3,5-dinitrobenzoate complexes are identified by the maximum absorption regions. The absorbances of the chelates are affected by the factors given below.

Influence of pH : The effect of pH is checked on the complex systems in a series of buffer solutions from pH 1.5-11.0. The absorbances increase with the increase of pH, reaching maximum at pH 9.1 with λ_{max} 217 nm in the case of Sc^{3+} -DNB, at pH 6.4 with λ_{max} 235 nm in the case of Y^{3+} -DNB,

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF THE STOICHIOMETRY, STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THE FREE ENERGY ($\Delta^\circ G$ IN kcal mol⁻¹ AT 25°) OF Sc³⁺-, Y³⁺-and La³⁺-DNB COMPLEXES

Method	Ratio	Sc ³⁺ -DNB		Y ³⁺ -DNB		La ³⁺ -DNB	
		K _f	$\Delta^\circ G$	K _f	$\Delta^\circ G$	K _f	$\Delta^\circ G$
M. R.	1 : 1	3.15 × 10 ⁷	10.29	2.31 × 10 ⁷	10.11	1.70 × 10 ⁷	9.92
	1 : 3	7.77 × 10 ¹³	27.30	1.67 × 10 ¹⁰	25.01		
C. V.	1 : 1			1.86 × 10 ⁷	9.98		
	1 : 2					6.67 × 10 ¹³	18.97
S. L.	1 : 3	3.96 × 10 ¹¹	29.64	4.72 × 10 ¹³	27.00	1.62 × 10 ¹⁰	22.25
	1 : 1	1.41 × 10 ⁹	12.56	6.76 × 10 ⁶	9.37	3.72 × 10 ⁷	10.39
	1 : 2			0.76 × 10 ¹⁰	13.56	1.30 × 10 ¹³	18.01
L. L.	1 : 3	0.62 × 10 ¹⁰	21.68	0.17 × 10 ¹⁵	19.53	1.38 × 10 ¹⁶	20.78
	1 : 1	0.20 × 10 ⁶	7.27	0.17 × 10 ⁶	5.79	0.15 × 10 ⁶	5.73
pH	1 : 2	0.38 × 10 ¹¹	14.52				
	1 : 1	1.05 × 10 ⁸	8.26	1.25 × 10 ⁹	12.48	3.17 × 10 ⁶	8.92

and at pH 8.59 with λ_{max} 220 nm in the case of La³⁺-DNB solutions. Thereafter, the absorbance falls perhaps due to formation of hydroxo species.

Influence of ligand concentration : At constant metal ion concentration and variable concentrations of DNBA using the respective concentration of reagents as blanks, absorbance values decrease with the increase of ligand concentration with a blue shift in λ_{max} (λ_{max} of Sc³⁺-DNB from 217 to 223 nm, λ_{max} of La³⁺-DNB from 220 to 262 nm).

Influence of metal ion concentration : On keeping the ligand concentration constant at $2 \times 10^{-5} M$ ([Sc³⁺] = 2×10^{-6} - $4 \times 10^{-5} M$); $1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ ([Y³⁺] = 5×10^{-6} - $5 \times 10^{-5} M$); and $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ ([La³⁺] = 1×10^{-6} - $1.3 \times 10^{-4} M$), the absorbances of the solutions increase with the increase of metal ion concentration. This may be due to the probable formation of complexes containing higher ratios of DNBA. λ_{max} of Y³⁺-DNB at lower concentrations 250 nm and that at moderate concentrations 235 nm, shift to 230 nm (hypsochromic shift) at higher concentrations of Y³⁺.

Conformity to Beer's law :

Beer's law is valid for introducing DNBA as a chelating agent for the microanalytical determination of 6.74-33.70 ppm Sc ($\epsilon=5333$); 4.45-71.20 ppm Y ($\epsilon=3200$); and 3.47-75.52 ppm La ($\epsilon=11000$ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹).

Stoichiometry of the complexes :

The stoichiometry of the complexes are evaluated making use of the results of conductivity and spectrophotometric measurements (molar ratio; M. R.¹⁰; continuous variation, C. V.^{11, 12}; straight line, S. L.^{13, 14}; and limiting logarithmic; L. L.^{15, 16} methods). The results are recorded in Table 1.

Apparent formation constant :

The apparent stability constants and the free energy changes ($\Delta^\circ G$) of the complexes are evaluated from the results of the spectrophotometric measurements¹⁰⁻¹⁶ and effect of pH on the absorption spectra of the chelates^{16, 17}. The free energy change of the chelates can be calculated applying the equation :

$$\Delta^\circ G = -RT \ln K$$

where, R=gas constant, T=(t+273 K) and K=dissociation constant of the complex.

The results of the stoichiometry, stability constant and the free energy of the chelates are collected in Table 1.

The complexation between 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid and Sc³⁺, Y³⁺ and La³⁺ takes place through covalent bond forming salt like complexes. Thus, bonding of the ligand and the metal ions can be represented as follows :

M³⁺-DNB (1 : 3) complex.

References

1. W. BRUN, U. S. Patent, 1, 971, 029, Aug. 21, (1934).
2. A. M. LAVENCHY, *Anales Fac. Quim. Y. Farm., Univ. Chile*, 1959, 11, 54.
3. R. M. AWADALLAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 60.

4. R. M. AWADALLAH, M. K. SHERIF and A. A. M. GAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).
5. R. M. AWADALLAH, M. K. SHERIF and A. A. M. GAD, *Asw. Sci. Techn. Bull.*, 1983, 4, 1, 23.
6. R. M. AWADALLAH, M. K. SHERIF and A. A. M. GAD, *Asw. Sci. Techn. Bull.*, 1983, 4, 1, 11.
7. A. K. PANDEY, M. CHANDRA, B. V. AGARWALLA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 32.
8. Illinois Institute of Technology, Chicago, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 757.
9. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", 4th ed., Van Nostrand, 1956, Vol. 1.
10. YOE and JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
11. P. JOB, *Compt. Rend. (Paris)*, 1925, 180, 928 ; *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, 9, 133.
12. W. C. VOSBOURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437.
13. E. I. ASMUS, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 178, 104.
14. KORKUC, A. SOMMER and T. LIPIEC in "Theory and Structure of Complex Compounds", ed. TRZEBIATOWAKA, Pergamon Press, 1962.
15. H. E. BENT and C. L. FRENCH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 568.
16. R. M. AWADALLAH, M.Sc. Thesis, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt, 1971.